

Development of a Laparoscopic Needle Driver with Decoupled Wrist and Rolling Capabilities

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Fig. 1: Standard EndoWrist of da Vinci Surgical System [2]

Abstract—This paper presents a design of a miniature gripper that can drive a suture needle in Robot-assisted Surgery. The presented gripper has two more advantages over the standard needle driver of da Vinci surgical robot. Firstly, it has a decoupled wrist that allows all joints to rotate independently with no coupling between them. This in turn lets the control strategy to be less complicated. Secondly, it has rolling capabilities, similar to the human hand, that allow re-orienting the needle with only two fingers. The gripper is rapid prototyped and tested to validate the proposed design. In the first experiment, the gripper is actuated about the wrist while the end effector position is measured and compared with the expected trajectory. The results showed that the wrist is completely decoupled from the other joints, as only a slight variation of 1% was obtained. In the second experiment, the rolling capability is tested in presence of a surgical needle.

Index Terms—Laparoscopic tool, needle driver, robotic surgery

I. INTRODUCTION

Robotic surgery offers many benefits to physicians and patients. It allows surgeons to conduct operations in hard-to-reach areas through tiny incisions with precise movements. The benefits for patients include less blood loss, less post-operative pain, and less risk of infection. Motivated by these advantages, robotic surgery has been adopted by many hospitals all over the world. It has been reported in [1] that worldwide da Vinci robotic procedures in 2021 grew approximately 28% compared with 2020, and the increase in shipping new da Vinci systems during the same period was up to 44%.

To enhance the robot's dexterity and expand the range of procedures that can be performed, surgical tools are contin-

uously improved [3]. By design, the joints of the standard tool, currently used by da Vinci robot Fig. 1, are mechanically coupled i.e. when the wrist is actuated, the joints on the yaw axis will undesirably rotate. This problem is solved electronically by coordinating the control of the actuators to compensate for the undesired motion. However, mechanically decoupled joints are preferred to coupled but electronically coordinated joints for three reasons. Firstly, grippers with decoupled wrist require less complicated control scheme as each joint is actuated independently [4]. Secondly, from safety point of view during surgical operations, it has been reported that decoupled mechanisms are preferred to be used in tools and instruments [5]. Thirdly, the interaction forces between the gripper and environment can be directly estimated by measuring the tension in the drive cables [6].

In the literature, several grippers with mechanically decoupled joints have been presented [7], [4], [8], [9] but with some associated flaws such as limited operating range, reduced device reliability, and design complexity. A new concept of decoupled grippers was presented in [10] and [11]. In this concept, the tendons were routed through the symmetry plane of the tool wrist. The tendons extended from the centre of the wrist to the graspers across non-movable pulleys. The grippers were compact and with a fewer mechanical parts. On the other side, one of the missing functionalities in surgical grippers is the ability to roll an object in a similar manner to the human hand (see Fig. 2). Such a rolling capability is quite helpful as surgeons need to change frequently the needle orientation. A new needle driver with rolling capabilities was presented for the first time in our previous work [12]. The only concern was the mechanical coupling between the wrist and yaw joints which complicates the control strategy.

In this research, a modified design of our tool, that has been presented previously in [12], is proposed to have a decoupled wrist along with its rolling capability. The proposed design is based on the approach of routing the tendons through the symmetry plane of the gripper wrist across fixed posts.

The remainder of this article is organized as follows. Section II describes the prior design and the joint coupling of the tool. Section III presents the new gripper with decoupled mechanism. Section IV presents the prototype, experiments and results. Finally, section VII concludes this article.

Fig. 2: Human hand rolling capabilities

Fig. 3: Prior design with coupled wrist [12].

Fig. 4: Joint coupling in the prior design.

II. COUPLING IN PRIOR DESIGN OF THE TOOL

A. Design description

Fig. 3 shows the previous design of the tool where the joints of the wrist and yaw axes are mechanically coupled. The two graspers $5A_n$ and $5B_n$ rotate about the yaw axis with the help of the two pulleys $6A_n$ and $6B_n$. The rotation of the

central pulley 7_n drives the two graspers to move linearly in different directions. The linear motion of the graspers causes the rolling of the needle as shown in Fig. 3(d). The mechanism that converts the rotation of the pulley into a linear displacement is illustrated in Fig. 3(c). In this mechanism, the two eccentric cylinders of the central pulley, (7_n-1 Fig. 3(c)), rotate eccentrically inside the slots of the graspers. Due to the phase shift of 180° between the two cylinders, one of the graspers moves up and the other moves down.

The actuation of the three pulleys $6A_n$, $6B_n$ and 7_n is made by three pairs of tendons. The tendons are extended from the wrist to the graspers across a set of idler pulleys as shown in Fig. 4. The gripper wrist is actuated by an additional pair of tendons.

B. Joint coupling Analysis

Fig. 4(a) and 4(b) show the routing of the tendons through the idler pulleys before and after the actuation of the wrist. It is shown that when the gripper rotates about the wrist axis, an additional part of the tendon (see the red part in Fig. 4(a) and 4(b)) wraps around the wrist pulley. Consequently, the pulleys $6A_n$, $6B_n$, and 7_n will rotate with an angle φ to compensate the wrapped part of the tether.

III. NEW DESIGN WITH DECOUPLED WRIST AND ROLLING CAPABILITIES

Fig. 5 shows the proposed design where the tendons are extended through the plane of symmetry of the tool from the wrist link to the driven pulleys on yaw axis. The wrist link has 3 pairs of holes through which the 3 pairs of the driving tendons are routed. A set of crimp sleeves are used to connect the ends of the tendons to the driven pulleys. The green and black tendons are connected to the two pulleys by which the two graspers can rotate about the yaw axis. The yellow tendon is connected to the central pulley that drive the graspers to make the linear displacement. While the brown tendons, shown in Fig. 5(b) and 5(c), drive the gripper to rotate about the wrist axis. Fig. 6 shows the rotation of the gripper about the wrist axis with no change in the lengths of the tendons at any rotational angle. Fig. 6(b), 6(c) and 6(d) show the bending of the tendons at the curved edges of the fixed posts.

IV. PROTOTYPING AND TESTING

Fig. 7 shows the 3D printed prototype of the new tool with decoupled wrist mounted on the driving unit. The two graspers and their driving pulleys are printed in metal to provide strong grasping force. The five motors of the actuation unit are used to drive-by-wire the five degrees of freedom of the gripper. As shown in the experimental setup, the motors of the driving unit are powered by 5v DC power supply, and controlled by the development kit of Arduino Mega.

In the first experiment, a set of angles ranging from 20° to 160° are sent as references to the motor of the wrist. At the same time, the distance of the end effector with respect to the wrist axis is measured at some selected angles. In the new decoupled design, when the wrist is actuated, the

Fig. 5: New tool design with decoupled wrist

graspers will not bend. As such, the distance from the end effector to the wrist should be always same at any angle of rotation. Fig. 8 shows the rotation of the gripper about the wrist axis while the measured distance is represented by a yellow line. The measuring points are made clear by adding two markers, i.e. green and red. The graph shown in Fig. 8 represents the measured distances in the whole range of the gripper rotation. According to the kinematic model, the distance between the end effector and wrist axis should be always 19.2 mm; represented by the blue line in the graph. The graph shows that the measured distance (the red line) is fluctuating around 18.9 mm with slight variation of 1%. This variation is due to the inaccuracies of the measurement process as the yellow line is extended manually between the measuring points after importing the image into the Matlab workspace. On the other hand, the graph shows a slight difference of around 0.3 mm between the estimated distance and the average of the measured distances. This difference is due to the misalignment between the graspers and the wrist link at the beginning of the experiment as the assembly of the

Fig. 6: The gripper rotation about the wrist axis is decoupled from all other joints. The tendons seem to have a sharp bending due to the very small radius of the fixed tubes.

gripper is made manually. In the second experiment, the tool rolling capability is tested successfully in presence of a suture needle as shown in Fig. 9.

V. CONCLUSIONS

The design and prototyping of a surgical gripper with decoupled wrist and rolling capabilities are presented in this work. The gripper can be used as a needle driver in robotic-assisted surgeries. The decoupling mechanism is designed based on the approach of routing the tendons through the plane of symmetry of the gripper wrist across fixed posts. The proposed design is validated with two experiments; in the first experiment the gripper is actuated to rotate about the wrist axis, and at the same time the distance between the end effector and wrist axis is measured. The results validate the proposed decoupling mechanism as the measured distance did not show significant change over the range of rotation. On the other hand, the gripper could successfully use its rolling capabilities to change the orientation of a suture needle.

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Fig. 7: The experimental setup. The actuation unit drives-by-wire the tool DOFs while the motors are controlled by an Arduino board.

Fig. 8: The results of the first experiment; the gripper is actuated about the wrist while the distance from the end effector to the wrist axis is measured. At any angle of rotation, the distance is almost constant with slight variation of 0.01.

Fig. 9: The rolling capabilities of the gripper is demonstrated in presence of a suturing needle

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